

Survey Instruments

1. Teacher Questionnaire

Survey on the Professional Training of International Graduate Students in Engineering Disciplines in China (Faculty Version)

Instructions

Dear Professor,

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this survey. This questionnaire aims to investigate the current status of professional training for international graduate students in engineering disciplines in China, with the goal of providing empirical evidence for improving training quality.

This survey is conducted anonymously. No personal identifying information will be collected, and all data will be used solely for academic research purposes. Completion of the questionnaire will take approximately 5–8 minutes. We sincerely appreciate your support and cooperation.

Part I. Background Information

1. **Gender**

Male Female

2. **Age**

_____ years

3. **Academic Title**

Lecturer / Assistant Researcher

Associate Professor / Associate Researcher

Professor / Researcher

Other (please specify): _____

4. **Institution / School**

5. Disciplinary Field

6. Number of International Graduate Students Supervised

_____ students

7. Graduation Requirements at Your Institution (Multiple choice)

- Completion of required credits
- Passing mid-term or comprehensive assessments
- Publication of academic papers
- Completion and defense of a thesis
- Other (please specify): _____

Part II. Training Objectives and Practical Needs

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements

(1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree).

8. The institution cultivates international students' ability to acquire knowledge through analysis, investigation, and inquiry.

1 2 3 4 5

9. The institution cultivates international students' solid foundational knowledge and scientific research competence.

1 2 3 4 5

10. The institution cultivates international students' practical abilities, such as conducting innovative experiments and solving complex problems.

1 2 3 4 5

11. The institution cultivates international students' academic expression, communication skills, and ability to write standardized academic papers.

1 2 3 4 5

12. The training objectives meet the talent needs of international students' home countries.

1 2 3 4 5

13. The training objectives meet international students' personal development needs.

1 2 3 4 5

Part III. Evaluation of the Curriculum System

(1 = Very Dissatisfied / Strongly Disagree, 5 = Very Satisfied / Strongly Agree)

14. Scientific rigor and rationality of the curriculum structure.

1 2 3 4 5

15. Richness and practical relevance of course content.

1 2 3 4 5

16. Satisfaction with academic assessment methods (e.g., exams, papers, reports).

1 2 3 4 5

17. Course content reflects recent developments in the discipline and industry.

1 2 3 4 5

18. Courses provide sufficient international perspectives and interaction opportunities.

1 2 3 4 5

19. Courses help students build solid theoretical foundations and systematic professional knowledge.

1 2 3 4 5

20. Courses enhance independent thinking and further knowledge expansion.

1 2 3 4 5

21. Course knowledge can be effectively applied to research and academic writing.

1 2 3 4 5

Part IV. Evaluation of International Students' Core Competencies

22. **Key attributes you value most** (Multiple choice)

- Chinese language proficiency
- Educational background
- Academic performance
- Research potential
- Cross-cultural adaptability
- Learning attitude and motivation
- Other (please specify): _____

(1 = Very Poor, 5 = Very Good)

23. Foundational knowledge and abilities upon entry.

1 2 3 4 5

24. Academic research ability and innovation capacity.

1 2 3 4 5

25. Practical and hands-on abilities.

1 2 3 4 5

26. Cross-cultural communication ability.

1 2 3 4 5

27. Learning attitude.

1 2 3 4 5

28. Academic outputs and thesis quality.

1 2 3 4 5

Part V. Supervisor Guidance and Self-Evaluation

29. I provide research guidance tailored to international students' backgrounds and interests.

1 2 3 4 5

30. I encourage participation in academic conferences and international exchanges.

1 2 3 4 5

31. Frequency of face-to-face supervision

- Multiple times per week
- Once per week
- Once per month
- Several times per semester
- Rarely

32. I pay attention to students' psychological well-being and provide support.

1 2 3 4 5

33. I provide guidance on employment and career development.

1 2 3 4 5

34. Major challenges in current training (open-ended)

35. Suggestions for improvement (open-ended)

End of Questionnaire

Thank you again for your valuable time and support.

2. Student Questionnaire

Survey on the Professional Training of International Graduate Students in Engineering

Disciplines in China (Student Version)

Instructions

Dear Student,

This questionnaire aims to understand the current status of professional training for international graduate students in engineering disciplines in China. The survey is anonymous, and all information will be used solely for academic research. Completion takes approximately 8–10 minutes. Thank you for your participation.

Part I. Background Information

1. Gender
 Male Female

2. Age
 20–25 26–30 31–35 Above 35

3. Degree Level
 Master's Doctoral

4. Degree Type
 Academic Professional

5. Year of Study
 First Second Third Fourth or above

6. Country of Origin: _____

7. Major: _____

8. University: _____

9. Graduation Requirements (Multiple choice)
 Publication of journal articles
 Attendance at academic conferences
 Completion of required credits
 Thesis defense
 Other: _____

10. Intended Career Path

- Employment Further study Entrepreneurship
 Return to home country Other

11. Preferred Work Location

- China Home country Third country Undecided

Part II. Training Objectives and Actual Needs

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements

(1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree).

12. The university cultivates international students' ability to acquire knowledge through analysis and investigation.

- 1 2 3 4 5

13. The university cultivates international students' ability to master solid foundational knowledge and conduct scientific research.

- 1 2 3 4 5

14. The university cultivates international students' practical ability to carry out innovative experiments and solve complex problems.

- 1 2 3 4 5

15. The university cultivates international students' academic expression, communication, and academic writing skills.

- 1 2 3 4 5

16. The training objectives of this major meet the talent needs of my home country.

- 1 2 3 4 5

17. The training objectives of this major meet my personal development needs.

- 1 2 3 4 5

18. In addition to major courses, what other knowledge or skills would you like to acquire?

(Multiple choice)

- Chinese language
- Chinese history and culture
- Professional skills or certifications
- Cross-cultural communication
- Career planning and job-seeking skills
- Other (please specify): _____

Part III. Curriculum System Evaluation

Please indicate your level of satisfaction or agreement

(1 = Very Dissatisfied / Strongly Disagree, 5 = Very Satisfied / Strongly Agree).

19. Scientificity and rationality of the curriculum system.

1 2 3 4 5

20. Richness and usefulness of course content.

1 2 3 4 5

21. Satisfaction with academic assessment methods (e.g., exams, papers, technical reports).

1 2 3 4 5

22. Teachers clearly explain key points and course content.

1 2 3 4 5

23. Course content reflects the latest developments in the discipline and industry.

1 2 3 4 5

24. Courses provide sufficient international perspectives and interaction opportunities.

1 2 3 4 5

25. Courses help me build a solid theoretical foundation and systematic professional knowledge.

1 2 3 4 5

26. Courses help me develop independent thinking and expand course-related knowledge.

1 2 3 4 5

27. Course knowledge can be applied to scientific research and academic writing.

1 2 3 4 5

28. Preferred Language of Instruction

Chinese only

English only

Bilingual instruction (Chinese & English)

Other (please specify): _____

Part IV. Supervisor Evaluation

Please indicate your level of agreement

(1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree).

29. My supervisor has a high academic level.

1 2 3 4 5

30. My supervisor can communicate fluently with me in English.

1 2 3 4 5

31. My supervisor provides adequate guidance in academic research.

1 2 3 4 5

32. My supervisor provides adequate guidance in career planning.

1 2 3 4 5

33. Frequency of Face-to-Face Supervision

Multiple times a week

Once a week

Once every two weeks

Once a month

Less than once a month

34. Overall Satisfaction with Supervisor

1 2 3 4 5

35. Part V. Learning and Communication Challenges

Please rate the following aspects

(1 = Very Difficult, 5 = Very Easy).

36. Verbal communication (daily and academic).

1 2 3 4 5

37. Understanding course content.

1 2 3 4 5

38. Adapting learning methods.

1 2 3 4 5

39. Adapting to life in China.

1 2 3 4 5

40. Managing psychological stress.

1 2 3 4 5

40. **Suggestions for improving the professional training of international graduate students in engineering disciplines** (open-ended)

End of Questionnaire

Thank you again for your valuable time and support.